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A NEW APPROACH FOR TEACHING MATERIAL SCIENCES AT THE AUTOMOTIVE ENGINEERING PROGRAMME OF FONTYS UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES

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ABSTRACT

The use of polymers for modern vehicle components brings about significant advantages for the appearance, comfort and safety of new cars. Understanding and knowledge of these concepts are important for versatile future automotive engineers. Previous evaluations showed that the more classic lectures setting was less motivating and engaging, and the content thought to lack relevance for this programme. The focus in this research is on the evaluation of the new design of the Material Sciences course.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Importance of material science in Automotive Engineering curriculum

A wide variety of polymer materials are used to make vehicle components. The use of polymers brings about significant advantages for the appearance, comfort and safety of new cars. The manufacturing methods required to produce those materials vary greatly. In view of environmental issues, recycling becomes more relevant nowadays. Understanding and knowledge of these concepts are important for well-rounded future automotive engineers.

Previous evaluations of the Material Sciences course showed that the more classic lectures setting was experienced as less motivating and engaging by the students. Also, the content was deemed less relevant for the study of Automotive Engineering. At this moment, the learning output is therefore broad and shallow, and not specific enough for the challenges of an automotive engineer.

1.2 Research question

The question was raised as to whether or not a new format of the Material Sciences course could work better. After the first implementation, the focus here is on the evaluation of the new design of the Material Sciences course: Are the learning goals

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achieved with this new design, such that the students get more specific knowledge for an automotive engineer?

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 New design according to the principles of the constructive alignment

According to the principles of the constructive alignment [1], how students study is driven by examination. Students focus on achieving the learning objectives if you set the examination up in such a manner that it measures the achievement of the learning objectives. The design of a course begins with determining the learning objectives, then the examination, followed by what the learning activities must involve in order to reach the desired learning objectives. Finally, the teaching materials and the teaching activities are designed. These principles are followed in redesigning the Material Sciences course.

The specific components of the Material Sciences course, according to the systematics of the constructive alignment, are:

Learning objectives: The students will (learn to) research one specific topic in the field of polymers used in the automotive industry. They can choose between car paint, car wraps, brake pads, helmets, Marlon/Lexan window glass, airbags, spoilers, isolation materials, head-and-neck-support, race overalls, and upholstery. For these materials, the students will determine their specific chemical composition, together with the physical and chemical properties. The students will explain related manufacturing and recycling techniques, how these materials are tested, and will present the most recent innovations trends. In a final report, the students will document all these aspects. During a poster market, the students will present their own work and will collect information from other students about other materials and applications in automotive engineering.

Assessment: A formative assignment, shortly after the start of the course, gives a quick feedback on the expected quality. The students will be able to immediately adjust their activities. For the summative assignment, there are two final products for this course, a report and a poster. The report contains a complete review of the polymers from their own topic, with all the subsequent perspectives. The poster supports free discussion with peers and faculty members during a poster market. The poster session is also meant as an important opportunity for the students to acquire information about the applications of polymers in other topics rather than their own. Both products, the report and the poster, are summatively assigned with rubrics [2] that closely follow the learning objectives.

Learning activities: The students work in small groups of 2-3 students, both face-to-face and digital. The students are helped with relevant workshops and with tailored support from a tutor. The students (learn to) look for and analyse relevant scientific information that they find in databases with scientific literature. Each group of students writes a report and makes a poster that presents the results.

Teaching materials: The students can use books and online databases, but can also consult their teachers.

Teaching activities: The teaching approach is based on inquiry learning [3], when students are presented with topics to be analysed and questions to be answered. Different teachers support the students during specific workshops with their own expertise (chemistry, material sciences, automotive, etc.) during the whole project. The students are instructed how to look for, to analyse and to judge relevant scientific information. The students are taught how to write a report, how to make a poster and how to present the results. This support can also be a drop-in tutoring hour.

2.2 Evaluation of the new design

The research focuses on the link between the learning goals and the actual knowledge of the students: not only were the final products quantitatively evaluated with rubrics, but also a qualitative research took place; teachers involved in the project and different students were extensively interviewed by the author. Their feedback will be used to adjust the learning activities in order to improve the match between the learning goals and the students' learning output.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Quantitative evaluation

The quantitative evaluation was done with rubrics [2]. The rubrics were formulated according to the learning goals and tested the achieved level. Each topic (polymer chemistry, manufacturing, testing, recycling, and present day innovations) and each final product (the quality of the report and the poster) were rated on a scale from 0 to 3. Zero points stated a non-existing item and three points stated an outstanding result. From the maximum of 21 points, each student had to achieve a minimum of 15 points. The students got two chances to complete the assignment. In the first round, a total of 29% of the students passed the evaluation (35 out of 122). The teachers gave feedback and the student subsequently got a second chance to improve. In the second round, a total of 68% (58 out of 85) of the students passed the evaluation. The quantitative evaluation says that 76% of the students achieved the learning goals.

3.2 Qualitative evaluation

The course was subsequently qualitatively evaluated by a series of extensive interviews with eleven students and three teachers. The majority of students found the new setting very attractive, more motivating and engaging than a classic lecture setting. The teachers share these opinions.

A question was if the students, at the end of the course, were still aware of the learning objectives and their achievements. The interviewed students stated that, from their own perspective, they had achieved the learning goals. There are though three noteworthy points:

Firstly, the students are not really aware of the learning objectives, but they all still report an achievement. That may bring the self-reflection in doubt. Secondly, they report that they split their own topic between the group members. Subsequently, only some of them fully reflected on all parts of their group's topic; the majority of them

only have knowledge of their own part. Thirdly, the poster session was meant for the students as the ideal moment to get knowledge on the applications of polymers in all the other topics. A poster session was for the majority of the students a new form of sharing and gathering knowledge. Therefore, they focused mainly on presenting their own work, but were not actively involved in gathering knowledge over other topics. The interviewed teachers notice two crucial aspects about the new design. Firstly, compared to the previous setting, the students now acquire more knowledge on their own topic, but they miss the overview of all topics. Secondly, the students are not able to place the information in a knowledge network, they see it as a stand-alone summation of facts. What the teachers miss are not only the cross-links between different parts of the same topic, but also the mutual links between different topics.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Previous evaluations of the Material Sciences course showed that the more classic lectures setting was less motivating and engaging, with a content deemed as less relevant for the study of Automotive Engineering. The question was raised as to whether or not a new design, following the principles of the constructive alignment, would work better. The evaluation of the new design was presented here.

On the one hand, the students think that they achieved the learning goals. On the other hand, the teachers do not give a positive answer for everybody when answering the research question “Are the learning goals achieved with this new design, such that the students get more specific knowledge for an automotive engineer?”.

The first recommendation is for the teachers to realise an even stronger link between the learning objectives, the examination, and the learning activities, according to the principles of the constructive alignment. The second recommendation is that the goal of the poster market must be formulated even more explicitly and, subsequently, the market must be built accordingly. The poster session has a very important role: the students acquire information about other topics other than their own from the other students. In the results reported here, this is not yet the case.

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